

THE IMPACT OF PRINCIPAL LEADERSHIP STYLES ON TEACHERS PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN JEDDAH, KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA

Hessa Fahad Albugamiⁱ

Faculty of Economic and Administration,
Department of Business Administration,
King Abdulaziz University,
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

This research aiming at investigating the impact of principals' leadership styles on elementary school teacher's performance in Jeddah city in (KSA). The current research utilized a quantitative method approach. The main instruments used in this study are questionnaires, and the teacher's evaluation card. The population comprises all males and females at elementary school in KSA, particularly in Jeddah city. Thus, the researcher used a sample size of (200) female and male schoolteachers from elementary schools in Jeddah city. Collected data is entered and treated by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Based on data analysis and discussion of the collected data, the researcher concluded with the following findings: Contingent reward leadership style is the top that practiced while individual consideration style has a strong positive impact on teachers' performance. Also, the study finds that gender as moderating factor has influenced on principal leadership style and vary due to gender differences. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended to use transformational leadership style to enable principal to manage the rapid change and bring teacher on-board to the Saudi vision 2030. Furthermore, school principal should higher their level of education to motivate teachers toward creativity and innovation.

JEL: I20, I21, H75

Keywords: leadership styles, teacher performance, leadership theories, transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, laissez-faire-leadership style, democratic leadership style, autocratic leadership style, gender, age, educational level

ⁱ Correspondence: email hessa.fahad89@gmail.com

1. Introduction

As discussed in many researchers the relationship between the leadership and teachers' performance seems comparatively simple and direct in approach. Whereas, in practice, it is the most complicated and unpredictable. Therefore, it requires a thoughtful and deep investigation. Moreover, there are several kinds of research which assure the strong connection between school leadership style and school performance. Ubben and Hughes (1992) observed that principals could design a school climate that develops the effectiveness and productivity of her/his teacher; therefore, the leadership style of the principal should identify school achievement and teachers' performance.

According to Reed (2005) the concept of leadership is regarded as a vital feature of the progress of each company because of its influences at employees' achievement. In a continuously and revolutionary changing in a societal, industrial, and technological environment, leadership is a more significant aspect of administration now than previously. While leaders are focused on making supplies collectively, forming plans, designing plus leading activities to manage recognized goals. Also, leadership makes the influencing role of the administration. As mentioned by Reed (2005) leadership enhances the effectiveness and proficiency of management and sustainable performance. According to Southworth (1995) the true leader guides into adequate production in education organizations. Manager in many organizations should be meeting various obstacles and restrictions because of the consequences on organizations' performance, units, and teams, as well as work atmosphere and mood. According to Marilyn (2006) leaders who would like the most valuable outcomes should not depend upon restricted leadership technique. Moreover, Clark and Clark (2010) declared that various people require various styles of management. As a model, a recently engaged person needs more extra guidance than an employee with prominent proficiency. A demotivated character needs various leadership techniques and direction than one with a great degree of motive. A director must hold exact knowledge of who his followers are, what they comprehend, and what they can achieve. Several scientists have maintained that there is no precise explanation for describing the complex phenom of leadership.

According to Judge (2004) leadership is the influence on the mobilization of others to launch collective action in pursuance of the common good. Therefore, school's management is a way of encouraging and assisting teachers and learners to work enthusiastically towards the realization of schools and educational goals (Judge, 2004). The clerk stated that leadership style is the method and approach in which a leader proposes direction, implements plans and motivates people to meet organizational goals. Moreover, (Okumbe, 1998) demonstrated that leadership styles to be recognized in this study are democratic, autocratic, laissez-faire and transformational leadership has been of interest among philosophers, historians, and academician. According to Burns (1978) the style of leadership may have a meaningful impact in motivating the team members in achieving shared objectives. Furthermore, (Nawaz, & Khan, 2016)

mentioned that the positive employee' work outcomes are regarded as one of the chief factors to achieve organizational goals. So, effective leaders have specific characters that enable them to influence followers. Most researchers consider leadership style as an important variable in determining employee performance as well as organizational performance. Stogdil (1950) revealed that the success of an organization is conditional on the ability of the leader in influencing employee practices. As mentioned by Mwita (2000) job performance is a multi-dimensional construct that influences the achievement of strategic organizational goals. Due to the above-mentioned, there is a significant importance of leadership style on the teacher's performance. Thus, in this study the researcher center on investigating the impact of principals' leadership styles on elementary school teacher's performance in Jeddah city in (KSA).

1.1 Statement of the Research Problem

The present study was assumed to distinguish the administrators' management styles and the influence they possess on the achievement of the elementary school teachers. Consequently, the information which was essential for this research were collected on self-governing variables, which was administration style, and on the subordinate variable, which regarded with teachers' achievement. Additionally, the study included the two variables, the independent and dependent to examine the extents to which leadership tendencies can change the achievement of teachers at elementary schools in Jeddah. Also, it seeks to understand the connection between principal's leader techniques and teachers' performances. Furthermore, the study aims at classifying the relationship between the leader gender and the teacher's performance.

There is no doubt that the elementary school administrators as a pedagogical guide perform a significant role in the progress of the institution. But, some of those leaders are always busy doing administrative stuff and frame strategies rather than doing their right jobs. Therefore, Nanson, (2010) showed that utmost heads are occasionally seen at their positions fulfilling their duties, they neither transfer duties nor fully interact with their teachers. Thus, the researcher is motivated to find out why do some teachers performance is lower in some elementary school in Jeddah while others are highly motivated to achieve their school goals. It should be noted that notwithstanding many pieces of research have been conducted on administration technique and instructor achievement. But, none of these investigations was performed in the Saudi setting particularly at elementary school in Jeddah city. So, the researcher motivated to carry out the current study. To sum up, the central investigation difficulty focuses on the fact that administrators are possibly not practicing the most relevant management styles in particular situations to improve the condition of education attainment of their teachers. It's estimated by the researchers that largest of the administrators who were operating with this researcher were consuming most of their time performing every day managing tasks in their positions, fairly than inspiring and motivating teachers to work carefully and achieve educational purposes by adopting the suitable teaching approaches. Another serious issue concerning the Saudi context,

there is no direct female school leaders at the elementary level which cause a huge gap in the leaders' duties and the consequences are lower teaching performance. The current situation and Saudi vision encourage women to take a real and serious role in Kingdom development. Therefore, women should have participated in the leadership position particularly in the educational field. Thus, this study examines whether gender difference affects the leadership style and teacher's performance in the educational field.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The objective of the current research is to investigate the leadership techniques used by school administrators and their impact on the job completion of elementary school teachers in Jeddah city in (KSA).

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This research aiming at obtaining a clear understanding of various types of leadership styles used at elementary school in Jeddah, the management style used, the perspicacity of the teachers and administrators regarding the kind of leadership styles that may influence teachers' performance. Therefore, the current study aims to:

- 1) Examine how do different leadership styles influence teachers' performance in elementary schools in Jeddah city.
- 2) Determine the most effective leadership style that has a positive impact on teachers' performance in elementary public schools in Jeddah city.
- 3) Examine whether the leadership styles differ according to leader gender or not.
- 4) Identify the extents to which the leader gender influences teacher performance.

1.4 Research Questions

Q1: How do different leadership styles influence teacher's performance in elementary schools' teachers in Jeddah city?

Q2: What is the most effective leadership style that has a positive impact on teachers' performance in elementary public schools in Jeddah city?

Q3: Do leadership styles differ according to leader gender?

Q4: To what extent does the leader gender influence teacher performance?

2. Literature Review and Previous Studies

2.1 The Concept of Leadership styles

According to Bennis (1959), there are as numerous descriptions of leadership as there are researchers who have attempted to examine and understand the concept, but there is no generally affirmed definition of it. Bennis explained that the word 'leader' originated from the root leaden which means 'to travel' or 'show the way'. It has been derived from the verb "to lead." This also suggests "to advance," "to expel," "to stand out," to guide and direct the works of others. A leader is a person who leads a group of

followers Bennis (1959). Hodge and Johnson (1970, p. 23) said that *“Leadership is essentially the ability to form the attitudes and behavior of other individuals, whether informal or formal situation and that management associate to the formal task of decision and command”*. Additional, Robbins (1996, p. 243) describes leadership as *“the capability to influence a group towards the attainment of goals”*. Additionally, Robbins added that leadership is the interpersonal influence exercised in a situation, and directed, through the communication process, towards the accomplishment of a specific goal or goals. Furthermore, Northouse (2013, P.3) described leadership as a process by which an individual influence a group of individuals to realize a common goal. Moreover, Jago (1982) revealed that leaders carry out this process by implementing their leadership knowledge and skills. This is called process leadership. Though, we know that we have features that can influence our actions. This is called trait leadership (Jago, 1982) in that it was once popular to believe that leaders were born rather than made. (Northouse, 2013, p.5) Tannenbaum, Weschler, and Massarik, 1961, p. 24) mentioned that leadership is *“interpersonal influence, exercised in a situation, and directed, through the communication process, toward the accomplishment of a specified goal or goals”*. Jacobs (1970, p. 232) defined leadership as *“an interaction between persons in which one presents information of a sort and in such a manner that the other becomes convinced that his outcomes will be improved if he behaves in the manner suggested or desired”*. According to (Stogdill, 1989, p. 411) leadership is *“the beginning and continuance of structure in expectation and interaction”*. Furthermore, (Terry. 1977, p. 45) stated that leadership is *“the relationship in which one person, the leader, leads others to work together willingly on related tasks to achieve that which the leader wishes”*.

2.2 Leadership Theories

Table 1.1: Leadership Theories

The Theory		Period	Summary of the Theory
Great Man Theory		Before 1950	Leader decides course of the history.
Traditional Leadership Theories	Trait Approach	Between 1910-1940	General and common characteristics of the leader is explained.
	Behavioral Approach	Between 1940-1960	Behaviors of the leaders are told.
	Contingency Approach	Between 1960-1980	It is depending on the situation not leader behavior.
New (modern) Leadership Theories		From 1980s till today	It varies depending on the direction of change of the society. For example; Authentic leadership, charismatics leadership, servant leadership.

2.3 The Impact of age and gender on leadership style

To accomplish designed goals, leaders are concerned with understanding their employees in a better way. There are several studies on the impact of age and gender on the leadership style of the managers (Ojode et al., 1999). The differences in age and

gender impact leadership style and individuals' behaviors as well. (Belal et al., 2010) indicated that at certain situations and tasks the older people accomplish tasks better than youngsters. From efficiency point, it is common that the younger people do tasks more efficient than older people. In contrast, old people give better advices more than young ones due to experience.

Based on age of leaders and age group, the style of leadership may be different. It is stated, *"With an older leader, the team may be more open to a leader's transformational behaviors, because the team members may be more accepting of the leader's special status"* (Kearney, 2008). Nowadays, evidence for this relationship between age and leadership finds in professions that require a big amount of specialized knowledge expertise, such as in arts, politics, and sciences (Van Vugt, 2006). Cagle (1988) indicates age as one of the factors that identify the leadership style of the leader. In most of cultures, it is common that as people get older as they become aware due to more experience and exposure. For instance, in African culture, experience is considered as a result of age and consequently older people is given the priority for leadership positions in organizations (Ahiazu, 1989).

Furthermore, it is common that males and females are leading from different points of perspectives. Winter and Waner (2001) indicate that *"Current psychological research on leadership and team interaction suggests that men and women exhibit different leadership styles and interpersonal communication styles in a variety of small-group situations from student problem-solving situations to industry and community situations"*. Based on common perception, females are more sensitive and less competitive than males. For example, (Beckman and Menkhoff, 2008) indicated that females significantly behave less competitive and more risk averse, try to avoid overconfident. Belal et al. (2010) concluded their study on Americans and Afghans that – Gender and Age – have their impact on the leadership styles of leaders. For this reason, it is very important to investigate the role of age and gender and its influence on the leadership styles of the leaders.

2.4 Previous Studies

(Jyoti and Dev, 2015) explored the relationship between transformational leadership and employee creativity. They found that there is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and employee creativity, and this relationship is moderated by learning orientation.

Furthermore, (Velju et al., 2017) studied the effect of the: autocratic, bureaucratic, charismatic, democratic, laissez-faire, transformational, and transactional leadership styles on employee performance at Business Organizations in Kosovo. The findings of the study showed that democratic, autocratic and transformational style have a positive effect on employee performance while charismatic, bureaucratic, laissez-faire and transactional leadership style have a negative effect. Moreover, (Malcalm, 017) examined leadership styles on employee performance in the public sector of Ghana. The

findings showed that the leadership style has no effect on the performance of the employees in the public sector.

Also, (Berson and Linton, 2005) examine the relationships between leadership style, quality, and employee satisfaction in Research and Development (R & D) versus a demonstration. This research centers on the next dimensions of leadership techniques: transactional, transformational leadership, and Laissez-faire leadership and non-transactional, and the research analyzed the relationship among leadership style and the demonstration of a quality environment in an R & D environment based on an experimental study consist of 511 research of engineers and scientists. It is determined that both transformational leadership and transactional contingent-reward leadership are linked to the establishment of a kind environment in the R & D part of a telecommunications company. The study noticed that the influence of transformational leadership styles is more notable to establish quality (Berson, 2003).

Furthermore, Ayene, (2016) examined the management styles selected by school principals and their impact on the job completion of elementary school teachers in Ethiopia, particularly in Tigray region. The study was intended to get insight into the sorts of leadership styles directly used, the leadership choice of principals, the thoughts of the instructors and principles concerning the leadership styles of the principals and the effect of the leadership styles on teachers' performance. The study came out with several findings. One of its findings showed that all leadership styles, except the directive leadership style, have a positive influence on the teachers' performance and the supportive leadership style is the most frequently used.

In educational sector, David and Obadia's (2017) examine the impact of leadership styles on the performance of primary school teaches in the Arusha District. The results of the study showed that the performance of teachers is great in the primary schools in the Arusha district. There is a significant correlation between transformational Leadership style and the performance of the primary school teacher, David and Obadia (2017).

In nursing sector, (Negussie and Demissie, 2013) investigate the correlation between leadership styles of nurse supervisors and nurses' job satisfaction in Jimma University Specialized Hospital. The outcome showed that nurses can favor a transformational leadership style over the transactional leadership style. In different fields, transformational leadership style dimensions were statistically significant and associated with both types of motivation and job satisfaction.

Moreover, (Muhammad et al., 2016) examine the influences of transformational leadership style on job satisfaction. The findings of the research showed that the transformational leadership style affects the job satisfaction and has a positive and significant impact, showing that the transformational leadership style is improved quality will change and develop employee satisfaction.

In GCC countries, especially in UAE, (Badreya Al-Jenaibi, 2014) investigate the behavioral and cultural problems that leaders meet while serving for multinational corporations, to investigate the degree to which different leadership styles impact

employee job satisfaction and organizational involvement United Arab Emirates UAE. The analysis revealed the following findings the consultative and consensus leadership styles are widespread among the United Arab Emirates construction section. Furthermore, the leadership strongly influenced worker job satisfaction.

Unlike other study in the same community, (Ibrahim, 2013) investigated whether a relationship exists between the principal's leadership style and both a performance level and the principal's effectiveness in schools in Dubai. Furthermore, it examined whether the correlation change according to the principal's gender, years of experiences and the level of school "*primary, intermediate, and secondary*". The study found a positive association between the school principal leadership style and his /her effectiveness. On the other hand, there was no connection with school performance. Lastly, (Ibrahim, 2013) concluded that the principal style and effectiveness vary due to the principal gender and level of the school, but not according to the principal's years of experience.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Methodology

The current research utilized a quantitative method that is going to be applied to obtain data from the chosen sample. These techniques helped in creating a base on a comprehensive perception of the study query.

3.2 Population and Sampling

In the present investigation, the population comprises all male and female at elementary school in KSA, particularly in Jeddah city. (Parahoo 2006, p.258) defines the population of the study as "*the whole number of systems of which data can conceivably be gathered*". Moreover, Proctor et al. (2010) declare that, in quantitative analysis, the scope and the size of the representation of the study should be determined at the prototype stage "*design stage*". Furthermore, (Polit & Beck, 2010) stated that quantitative researchers should choose the most comprehensive sample likely so that it describes and represent the whole population. Thus, the researcher recommended using a sample size of 200 female and male schoolteachers from elementary schools in Jeddah city based on Planning and Development Center report in Saudi Ministry of Education. The power reliability is nearly high because the chosen sample represents 85% of all teachers in this specific area. The researcher employed arbitrary selection technique to choose a sample of the study. Furthermore, 20 school principals were selected as benchmark to assess their leadership styles effect on the teacher's performances.

3.3 Source of Data

Both source of primary and secondary data is used to investigate the principal leadership style and the teachers' performance.

A. Primary Source of Data

Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) is used in order to collect age and educational level data of school principals and determine their leadership style.

B. Secondary Source of Data

Teachers performance evaluation cards are used as a secondary data to determine the effect of leadership style of the principal on her/his teachers' performance whether if it is positive or negative effect based on the total score of Teacher Performance Cards.

4. Results and Discussion

This section is mainly devoted to data analysis of the data collected through three methods from the participants of the study, including questionnaire and the teacher's evaluation card. The researcher obtains a round (200) reports for teacher performance evaluation cards. Also, the researcher gathered about 20 responses from the school principals regarding their leadership styles. The data collected by the survey instruments, and the evaluation card entered into (SPSS) for statistical treatment and producing the outputs in order to answer the main research question. Suitable statistical methods used to include the descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The statistical analysis in this section will proceed to cover the assessment of the sample responses towards the survey questionnaire dimensions.

4.1 Results of Research Question 1

This part of data analysis is devoted to answer the following research question: How do different leadership styles influence teacher's performance in elementary schools' teachers in Jeddah city?

Table 4.1: multiple regression analysis to examine how do different leadership styles influence teachers' performance in public elementary schools in Jeddah

Model	Coefficients	Beta	T-test	Sig.	F	Sig.
Constant	49.06		11.945**	0.00	21.945**	0.00
Idealized influence	-2.08	-0.194	-1.01	0.33		
Inspirational motivation	3.97	0.381	1.12	0.29		
Intellectual stimulation	-2.17	-0.196	-1.01	0.33		
Individual consideration	7.11	0.696	3.26**	0.007		
Contingent reward	1.67	0.175	0.603	0.56		
Management-by-exception	4.55	0.462	3.02**	0.01		
Laissez-faire leadership	0.404	0.071	0.618	0.55		
R = 0.963	R2 = 0.928			Adj. R2 =0.885		
	Durbin-Watson = 2.031					

**indicated that F-value & T-test are significant at the (0.01) level.

The results of multiple regression analysis in table (4.1) revealed that the F-value is significant at the (0.01) level, which indicated that, the multiple regression model used is efficient to estimate the effect of the factors of leadership style on teachers'

performance in elementary schools at Jeddah. In addition to that the results show that the value of determination coefficient is equal to (0.928) which indicated leadership factors included in the model have to influence of teachers' performance by 93.0%.

From the results in the table, also we notice that there are only two factors that had a statistically significant influence on teachers' performance. The first factor is the individual consideration, and the second factor is management by exception. Therefore, these two factors responsible of the most change in teachers' performance, while other factors have no statistically significant influence on teachers' performance, as the (P-values) are greater than (0.05) level.

Thus, we conclude that, the individual consideration, and management by exception are considered as the only two factors that influence significantly on teachers' performance, and this may be mainly related to that school principals give more attention to individual consideration, and practice the style of management by exception. This result was supported by Northouse's (2007, p.3) who described leadership as a process by which an individual influence a group of individuals to realize a common goal. Moreover, Jago (1982) revealed that leaders carry out this process by implementing their leadership knowledge and skills. This is called process leadership. Though, we know that we have features that can influence our actions.

4.2 Results of Research Question 2

This part of data analysis is devoted to answer the following research question: What is the most effective leadership style that has a positive impact on teachers' performance in elementary public schools in Jeddah city?

The results in Table 4.2, examines the influence of leadership style factors on performance, the results found that, individual consideration, and management-by-exception, are only the two factors that positively and significantly impact on teachers' performance in elementary public schools in Jeddah city.

Table 4.2: Multiple regression analysis to examine how leadership influences teachers' performance in public elementary schools in Jeddah

Model	Coefficients	Beta	T-test	Sig.	F	Sig.
Constant	49.06		11.945**	0.00	21.945**	0.00
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Inspirational motivation	3.97	0.381	1.12	0.29		
Intellectual stimulation	-2.17	-0.196	-1.01	0.33		
Individual consideration	7.11	0.696	3.26**	0.007		
Contingent reward	1.67	0.175	0.603	0.56		
Management-by-exception	4.55	0.462	3.02**	0.01		
Laissez-faire leadership	0.404	0.071	0.618	0.55		
R = 0.963	R2 = 0.928			Adj. R2 =0.885		
	Durbin-Watson = 2.031					

**indicated that F-value & T-test are significant at the (0.01) level

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is efficient to estimate the effect of the factors of leadership style on teachers' performance in elementary schools at Jeddah. In addition to that the results show that the value of determination coefficient is equal to (0.928) which indicated leadership factors included in the model have to influence of teachers' performance by 93.0%.

From the results in the table, also we notice that there are only two factors that had a statistically significant influence on teacher's performance. The first factor is the individual consideration, and the second factor is management by exception. Therefore, these two factors responsible of the most change in teachers' performance, while other factors have no statistically significant influence on teachers' performance, as the (P-values) are greater than (0.05) level.

Thus, we conclude that, the individual consideration, and management by exception are considered as the only two factors that influence significantly on teachers' performance, and this may be mainly related to that school principals give more attention to individual consideration, and practice the style of management by exception. This result was supported by Northouse's (2007, p.3) who described leadership as a process by which an individual influence a group of individuals to realize a common goal. Moreover, Jago (1982) revealed that leaders carry out this process by implementing their leadership knowledge and skills. This is called process leadership. Though, we know that we have features that can influence our actions.

4.3 Results of Research Question 3

This part of data analysis is devoted to answer the following research question: Do leadership styles differ according to leader gender?

Table 4.3: Independent sample T-test to examine if there is statistically significant variation between leadership styles related to gender

	Gender				T-Test	P-value
	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Idealized influence	3.78	0.21	3.12	0.39	4.75**	0.00
Inspirational motivation	3.71	0.18	3.40	0.41	2.19*	0.04
Intellectual stimulation	3.36	0.27	3.53	0.36	-1.236	0.23
Individual consideration	3.35	0.28	3.20	0.53	0.796	0.44
Contingent reward	3.50	0.27	3.40	0.56	0.480	0.64
Management-by-exception	3.39	0.20	3.20	0.36	1.457	0.16
Laissez-faire leadership	3.35	0.31	3.07	0.44	1.670	0.11
Overall (leadership style)	3.49	0.09	3.28	0.34	1.979	0.06

**indicated that the difference is significant at the (0.01) significant.

The results in Table 4.3, show that, there are statistically significant difference between principals regarding the influence of gender on their leadership style. The results showed that male principals are practicing Idealized Influence factor more than other factors. Idealized Influenced is one of Transformational leadership style element where principals transform to behave ideal behaviors that result in their being role for their

teachers. Unlike female principals who are practicing Contingent Reward more than other factors. Under this factor, principals focus on enhancing teacher's performance to take control of their tasks. Contingent Reward is one of transactional leadership style element which is the opposite side of Transformational style. This result was supported by (Shaikah, Ibrahim, 2013) who concluded that the principal leadership style and effectiveness vary due to the principal gender and level of the school, but not according to the principal's years of experience.

4.4 Results of Research Question 3

This part of data analysis is devoted to answer the following research question: To what extent does the leader gender influence teacher performance?

Table 4.4: results of independent sample T-test
 to examine if gender influence teachers' performance

	Gender				T-test	Df	P-value
	Male (100)		Female (100)				
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Teachers' performance	92.20	4.52	83.60	5.04	4.02**	198	0.001

The results in table 4.14 show that the value of T-test is reaching (4.02) which is significant at the (0.01) significant level. This indicated that, there is a statistically significant difference between teachers' performance related to leader gender. Therefore, we conclude that the leader gender has to influence significantly on teachers' performance in female and male elementary schools in Jeddah city. In addition to that it is obvious that, the significant difference is positive to the side of male leader. In addition, regarding gender effect, the researcher finds that the male principals are more flexible than female principals. For example, during the process of data collection the male principals are helpful and cooperated with researcher regarding the permission for collecting data. They satisfy with a formal letter from the director of planning and development of the Ministry of education and pave the researcher way to gather the data easily. Whereas, the majority of the female principals complicated the procedures and hiders the data collection process by asking the researcher to bring various letters from the different manager which represents challenge and barrier that hinders the data collection process. from here we understood female principals were not flexible in their management which indicates that the follow dictatorial leadership style which might affect their teachers' performance.

5. Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

This section concludes the thesis by answering the research questions proposed at the beginning of the research. Then the findings discussion is presented and followed by proposed recommendation that will provide great input regarding leadership styles

and their impacts on the teacher performance. At the end of section, conclusion is drawn from this study. Also, it provides a suggestion for further studies.

5.1 Findings

Based on data analysis conducted in the previous section, the study finds, basing on answering Q1, that contingent reward is at the top of the leadership styles that practiced by schools' principals in Jeddah city schools, while the second leadership style is the inspirational motivation, whereas, the third one is the idealized influence, where is the intellectual stimulation is at the fourth level. This finding in agreement with (David and Obadia's, 2017) who examined the impact of leadership styles on the performance of primary school teaches in the Arusha District. The results of the study showed that the performance of teachers is great due to the positive impact of principal's leadership style.

The study also found that, the individual consideration, and management by exception are considered as the only two factors that influence positively and significantly on teachers' performance. This result doesn't correspond to (Ayene, 2016) study that conducted in Ethiopia, it came out with several findings, but the main finding was that all leadership styles, except the directive leadership style, have a positive influence on the teachers' performance.

In order to examine the impact of gender and answer Q3 and Q4, the results show that gender as moderating factor has influenced on principals' leadership styles and vary due to gender differences. To illustrate more, the study finds that female principals by practicing Contingent Reward style impact teacher performance in a positive way. In the opposite side, male principals who are practicing Idealized Influence style has a positive impact on their teacher performance. When two leadership styles that are different in their concentrations, but they have the same impact on employee's performance, it means that gender as a moderating factor impact the correlation between principal's leadership styles and teachers' performance. This finding is supported by the study of (Shaikah, Ibrahim, 2013) who concluded that the principal leadership style and effectiveness vary due to the principal gender.

The study examining of the influence of leader gender on teacher's performance, finds that there is statistically significant difference between teachers' performance related to gender as a moderating factor. This means that the leader gender has to influence significantly on teachers' performance in female and male elementary schools in Jeddah city. The study finds that there is statistically significant difference between principals regarding the influence of gender on their leadership style. The results showed that male principals are practicing Idealized Influence factor, which is one of transformational style, more than other factors. Unlike female principals who are practicing Contingent Reward more than other factors. It means that female principals focus on enhancing teacher's performance to take control of their tasks. Contingent Reward is one of transactional leadership style element which is the opposite side of Transformational style. In fact, this finding does not align with Eagly, Johannesen-

Schmidt, and Van Engen (2003) findings. For example, they found that female scored higher than male in Transformational leadership. Whereas, men scored higher than women in Transactional leadership style.

5.2 Conclusion

The results of this study show that there is strong and positive relationship between teaching performance, and school principal leadership style. In addition to that, it is noticed that, the strong and positive relationship is always in match with the Transformational leadership style, whereas the negative relationship, is matching with Laissez-faire leadership style. Furthermore, the study results reveal that there is statistically significant difference between teachers' performance related to gender, as a mediator variable. This means that the leader gender has a significant influence on teachers' performance in female and male elementary schools in Jeddah city. Lastly, the results explain that the most important things that the school principals should do to improve teaching performance include: the school principal should have a time to share ideas, offer training chances for all teaching staffs equally, use rewards to motivate teachers to improve their teaching practices.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the finding's discussion of the study, the researcher recommends the following recommendations:

- To improve teacher's performance, school principal should higher her/his level of education to be able to motivate teachers' school toward creativity and innovation.
- To "ride the wave" due to the rapid change of technology, the study recommends to use transformational leadership style which is the best style that enable leader to create and manage the change, and therefore bring teachers on-board to the new Saudi vision 2030.
- The school principal should not use the Laisser-faire and bureaucratic leadership styles due to their negative effects on teacher's performance and they don't increase the teacher performance.

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Hessa Fahad Albugami
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IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN JEDDAH, KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA

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